

LIFETIME PREDICTION AND IN SERVICE CONTROL OF CARBON FIBER COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber composite pressure vessels are presently in service providing storage for natural gas which is used to propel buses and other utility vehicles in Europe and elsewhere. These pressure vessels operate at pressures of up to 200 bars. They are also the best placed candidates for higher pressure applications for storing hydrogen for fuel cells. As with all pressure vessels these composite structures require periodic evaluation of residual minimum lifetimes in order to remain in service.

An analogy has been made between the behaviour of these filament wound structures and unidirectional composite specimens as the fibres in a pressure vessel are subjected to unidirectional loading. Failure processes in composite structures are diffuse and particularly damaging if the reinforcing fibers fail. The present study sets out to confirm the results of earlier studies that acoustic emission can be used to detect fibre failures, which can occur in unidirectional specimens even under steady loads which is analogous to a steady pressure in a vessel. The rate of emission of a unidirectional specimen and also filament wound vessels under a constant pressure obeys a simple law which allows the damage accumulation to be calculated as a function of time. A maximum damage threshold can be determined experimentally so that master curves corresponding to the damage accumulated under steady loading conditions over the lifetime required of the composite, can be calculated. A finite element analysis of the process governing this behaviour has shown that viscoelastic relaxation of the matrix around fibre breaks is augmented by the effects of interfacial debonding along part of the broken fibre near the break. A comparison between master curves and the rate of damage accumulation of any pressure vessel of the same type reveals if it will fail before or after the desired lifetime. The effects of pressure variations during service have been seen to be minor but even if this is not the case a comparison with the master curves still allows minimum lifetimes to be predicted. The technique does not require the vessels to be removed from the vehicle which is immobilised for a minimum of time.

KEYWORDS : carbon fiber composites, pressure vessels, minimum lifetime prediction, acoustic emission, fiber failure, matrix relaxation.

INTRODUCTION

The use of natural gas as a fuel for buses and trucks is increasing rapidly due to the relative low cost of the fuel and the absence of polluting by-products. The pressure vessels which are used to hold the gas under pressure have to be as light as possible so that high performance composites are an obvious choice. The pressure vessels are usually made of filament wound high strength carbon fibers in an epoxy matrix. In service these vessels are pressurised up to two hundred atmospheres. A typical bus will require nine such vessels, although some have more and each will have a capacity of around 135 litres. As with all pressure vessels legislation requires that they are subjected to a proof test after manufacture and then periodically tested, for example every three or five years, to determine whether

they can continue to be used until the next control. Standards and techniques exist for testing metal structures. These require the vessel to be pressurised to above (usually 1.5 times) the maximum pressure in service. Composite pressure vessels fail by the accumulation of a diffuse and global type of damage, of which the most important is the failure of fibers. A study of the probability of carbon fibre failure reveals that overloading a composite structure leads to an increase in the numbers of fibre breaks so an overload test, as required for a metal pressure vessel, is inappropriate (1). At present composite pressure vessels are subject to visual inspection to determine if any accidental damage such as by an impact has occurred. In the absence of obvious damage it has to be assumed that the vessel is as new. Visual inspection of composite structures is however extremely limited in use as an impact is most likely to produce delamination on the under face of the surface of the composite impacted and no external damage may be apparent. In addition the vessels should be removed from the vehicle which introduces the possibility of further damage being produced to the pressure lines.

Acoustic emission has been shown to be a useful technique for monitoring damage in composites and for identifying localised areas of damage. Many types of composite structures have been tested under cyclic and steady loads. In the case of carbon fiber reinforced composites, in which the fibers are arranged so as to be primarily loaded in tension, it is the reinforcements which determine the strength and rigidity of the structure. The failure of the structure, in this case, requires the fibers to fail. The acoustic emission technique can detect the failure of carbon fibers even though the fibers are of small diameter, usually $7\mu\text{m}$, and as they may occupy sixty percent of the volume of the structure the number of fibers in the composite is very great. It is generally assumed that, as carbon fibers do not show any viscoelastic behaviour, once a carbon fiber composite has been loaded in the direction of the fibers no further evolution of the material can be expected. It is true that no discernible overall creep is detectable in the fiber direction if the load remains constant. However it has long been known that damage in the form of fiber failures can be shown, by acoustic emission, to continue after a constant load has been applied, even in the case of unidirectional specimens loaded in the direction of the fibers (2). The damage mechanism which accounts for this behaviour has to involve the viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix material around sites of broken fibers (3). It has been previously shown that under a constant applied load the rate of fiber failure can be modelled mathematically and that a relationship between damage accumulation and the duration of the loading can be determined (4). The technique can therefore be used to monitor damage accumulation in carbon fiber composite pressure vessels and to allow minimum lifetimes to be predicted.

MATERIAL

Two types of carbon fibre reinforced epoxy specimens have been tested. Unnotched and rectangular, $270 \times 15 \times 0.9$ mm unidirectional cfrp specimens with a fibre volume fraction of 60 % have been tested. The fibres in these specimens were aligned parallel to the long axis and had to be broken for the composite to fail. These specimens were subjected to tensile loading. Pressure vessels made of carbon fibers, filament wound onto an aluminium liner, which served both as a mandrel and provided a gas proof seal, have also been tested and comparisons made between the behaviours of the two. A typical pressure vessel as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: A typical carbon fiber pressure vessel

After manufacture, the pressure vessels had been subjected to a hydraulic pressure test of 300 atmospheres, which corresponded to 1.5 times the operating pressure.

In this study damage occurring in the two types of specimens was monitored with a MISTRAS 2001 acoustic emission system which comprised two R15 piezoelectric transducer with a resonant frequency of 30KHz, and two preamplifiers with fixed gains of 40 dB. The use of two detection channels permitted the location of the events.

The pressurization of the vessels was carried out with the assistance of a hydraulic pump operating up to a maximum pressure of 1000 bars. The vessels were pressurised with water.

THEORY

Loss of residual strength and ultimate failure of a carbon fiber unidirectional or filament wound composite structures, in which the fibers are arranged so as to transfer maximum strength and rigidity, depends on the failure of the fibers. Figure 2a represents a unidirectional composite. The failure probability as a function of applied stress on the fibers, shown in Figure 2b, can be determined experimentally and is described by Weibull statistics, which gives the probability of fiber failure as :

$$P = 1 - \exp \left\{ - \int \left[\frac{\sigma - \sigma_u}{\sigma_o} \right]^m V \right. \quad (1)$$

Where P is the failure probability of a fiber of volume V, σ is the applied stress, σ_u the stress failure threshold and σ_o and m material constants. The factor m is the Weibull modulus and describes the dispersion of fiber strength.

Loading the composite in the direction of the fibers produces fiber breaks, as shown in Figure 3c, which are randomly distributed in the volume of the composite, in the absence of any stress concentration, as there is a wide dispersion of fibers strengths.

Figure 2a

Figure 2b

Figure 2c

Figure 2 : The composite structure is described as behaving as a unidirectional composite (Fig.2a). The failure of the fiber reinforcements is described by a probability curve as a function of applied stress as shown in Figure 2b leading to a random distribution of fiber breaks (Fig.2c).

Each fiber break is isolated from other breaks by the shear of the matrix which produces a load transfer along the fiber so that at a critical distance from the break the fiber is able to continue to support the load (6). This distance is given by :

$$l_c = \left[\frac{1}{2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right)} \ln \left(\frac{1}{V_f} \right) \frac{E_f}{G_m} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} r_f \quad (2)$$

where r_f, E_f are the radius and Young's modulus of the fiber

G_m the shear modulus of the matrix which varies as a function of time (t) due to relaxation

V_f the fiber volume fraction

and n the number of neighbouring fibers around the fiber break.

Each fiber break creates a damage zone, the limit of which is determined by the shear properties of the matrix and the Young's modulus of the fiber, as is illustrated in Figure 3 (6). In addition and importantly, there is a length of debond between the fiber and the matrix around the break which increases the load transfer length. The intact fibers neighbouring a broken fiber experience an increase in stress over a short length of each fiber as the total load supported by the plane passing through the fiber break has to remain unchanged. Shear stress relaxation of the matrix means that, with time, the lengths of the damage zones and the lengths of neighbouring intact fibers which experience increased stresses become longer.

Figure 3: Creation of a damage zone : Rosen's model.

As the probability of failure increases with fiber length, for a given stress, additional fibers fail which can be detected by acoustic emission and the damage zone increases in area. When the damage zones begin to interact damage accumulation accelerates and this represents the onset of instability which is taken as the definition of useful life of the pressure vessel.

The accumulation of fiber failures, detected as acoustic emission events, has been shown to obey a law of the following form :

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = \frac{A}{(t+\tau)^n} \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of acoustic emission events,

t is the time
 A is a factor which depends only on the applied stress
 τ is a time constant
 and n is a factor less than unity.

By defining an upper damage threshold as a maximum acceptable number of acoustic emission events it becomes possible to use equation (3) to create master curves for structures which have exactly the lifetimes required, as shown in the curve of acoustic emission as a function of time, in Figure 4.

Figure 4 : The accumulated AE events curve is compared to a master curve calculated for a life of 20 years. If the composite structure is acceptable for further use its curve should be lower.

If a unidirectional specimen or a pressure vessel is expected to survive for more than the twenty years considered with the master curve the acoustic activity detected from the structure under predetermined steady loading conditions must lie on a curve under the appropriate master curve. At any given time its rate of acoustic activity must be lower than that of the master curve. A comparison of the activity during a short period with the activity predicted by the master curve allows an evaluation of the residual lifetime of the pressure vessel to be made. If the number of emissions during the test is less than that given by the master curve the vessel is acceptable. If not it should either be changed or subjected to further examination (7).

Figure 5 :

Failure

Tests were carried out on pressure vessels at different pressures but as the maximum service pressure was 200 atmospheres particular attention was paid to vessels pressurised to this level. Figure 6 shows typical curve obtained with the pressure vessel at 200 bars.

Figure 6: Comparison between the experimental and theoretical curve of acoustic emission for different types of pressure vessel.

It can be seen that the results obtained from both types of specimens are very similar.

THEORETICAL MODELLING

The model describe above indicates that damage evolution, under steady loads, in unidirectional specimens loaded parallel to the fibre direction and by extension in the filament wound pressure vessels, occurs through the relaxation of the matrix around fibre breaks. This leads to increasing lengths of fibres neighbouring a break to be overloaded and so an increased probability of their failure. In order to begin to model this behaviour, the effects of a viscoelastic resin surrounding a fibre break have been modelled so as to reveal its effect on neighbouring fibres. Figure 7 shows a section of the composite and the distribution of the fibres and matrix. In places the fibres can be seen to be arranged in square and hexagonal patterns whereas elsewhere there are resin rich areas. A finite element model has been developed which supposes a regular average square distribution of the fibres.

Figure 7 : The fibres can be seen to be organised in a square or hexagonal pattern in parts of the composite but that there are also resin rich areas. An average square pattern has been modelled using finite element analysis.

The model has been used so as to investigate the overloading of the four fibres neighbouring a fibre break. A 3D network of has been used and the deformation around a broken fibre modelled by a progressive geometrical extension both parallel and normal to the fibre axis. The results show that the relaxation of the matrix around the fibre break induces an increase in load in neighbouring fibres over a distance which increases with time. This is shown in Figure 8 which also shows that stabilisation of the increase in stress occurs quickly. In order to obtain results which correspond to the real case it is necessary to take into account the debonding of the interface at the broken ends of the fibre. This has a marked effect on the level of stress experienced in the neighbouring intact fibres, as is shown in Figure 9. The length of interfacial debonding can increase in time which accounts for continuing fibre breaks observed in real specimens.

Figure 8 : The tensile stress in fibres neighbouring a fibre break, induced by the shear of the matrix and varying with time as the matrix relaxes.

Figure 9 : The increase in tensile stress experienced by a fibre neighbouring a fibre break. If the length of debonding is taken into account it can be seen that the overload is greater and distributed over a greater length of fibre.

Application to Pressure Vessels.

Pressure vessels are subjected in service to regular cycles of pressurisation and depressurisation. The model and experimental results expounded above show that damage will accumulate due to the relaxation of the resin around broken fibres. The failure of fibres is inevitable as soon as the vessel is pressurised due to the distribution of fibre strengths. Damage will continue to accumulate under constant pressure and if this continues long enough failure will occur. The rate of damage accumulation has been shown to be described by equation 3. A master curve can therefore be defined which describes the increase of damage in a pressure vessel which will last for exactly the period required of the vessel. After this period the damage zones which are distributed uniformly over the structure will start to interfere and the situation will become unstable with an increasing rate of damage occurring. This is taken to be the end of the useful life of the pressure vessel. Typically the service life of a pressure vessel will be twenty years and a master curve for this duration can be drawn using equation 3. Any pressure vessel which exhibits a rate of damage above that predicted by the master curve has to be considered as suspect and replaced.

It now becomes possible to draw curves which can be used in a practical tests. The numbers of emissions expected from the master curve depends on the length of time the control test is conducted and this can be chosen so as to accommodate the needs of the bus operator. The effect of pressure variations during service has been seen to be slight however the effect of pressurising the vessels three times each day over the lifetime of the vessel has been studied. Simulated full lifetime tests in which the pressure vessels have been repeatedly cycled from 15 to 200 atmospheres have been carried out. Periodically the cyclic tests have been stopped and the vessels subjected to a test at 200 atmospheres for twenty four hours.

Figure 10 shows the numbers of events recorded for one such test over a period of 100 000 cycles. It can be seen that the numbers of emissions recorded remained lower than the master curve up to 60 000 cycles but that at 100 000 cycles the activity had increased, showing that the vessel had become unstable, probably due to failure of the liner by fatigue.

Figure 10: Comparison of the master curve and experimental results showing that up to the equivalent of 60 years in service the pressure vessel tested emitted less than the master curve however after 10^5 pressure cycles, equivalent to one hundred years in service, the pressure vessel shows signs of instability and is no longer acceptable.

DISCUSSION

Experimental studies and theoretical modelling have shown that carbon fiber reinforced composites, in which the fibres are loaded in tension, continue to accumulate damage even under a constant load, or pressure, in the case of a pressure vessel. This damage can accumulate until it reaches a critical level at which the composite becomes unstable. The time dependant mechanism controlling delayed failures is the relaxation of the matrix around fiber breaks. This leads to the overloading of neighbouring intact fibers. As the strength of fibers shows a wide scatter a local increase in stress will inevitably cause further breaks which can be detected by the acoustic emission technique.

The accumulation of damage can be modelled to give the accumulation of damage as a function of time. Master curves can be drawn for pressure vessels with the lifetimes required. Pressure vessels at manufacture or in service can be controlled periodically by a comparison between their actual acoustic emission count in a given period and the count predicted by the master curve for the same period. If the actual count is less than the limit given by the master the pressure vessel is deemed acceptable for further service. If not it should be withdrawn from service.

The technique which is proposed allows the natural overall ageing of carbon fiber pressure vessels to be determined and minimum residual lifetimes calculated. The acoustic emission technique can also be used to locate localised damage which may occur for example due to an impact.

CONCLUSION

A non destructive evaluation technique has been developed for carbon fiber composite pressure vessels. The technique uses the acoustic emission technique to monitor damage accumulation during periods of steady pressure. A model based on the relaxation of the resin around fiber breaks has been described which accounts for the delayed failure of fibers which can eventually lead to failure of the pressure vessel. The number of counts recorded in a given period is compared to those predicted by

master curves and depending on whether the counts are below or above the master curve for the pressure applied the vessel is deemed acceptable for further service or not.

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